

Progress of Human Development in India: A Cross-Country Comparison with Survey Data

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The paper attempts to examine India's progress in the Human Development Index (HDI) in comparison to its neighboring countries over various periods. The study analyses the components of the Human Development Index (HDI) of India along with its neighbour countries for different years to observe the trend. Further, the study specifically analyses the human development components for India for different periods to observe the level of improvement of the indicators. The result shows that India belongs to the medium category of human development and is placed behind China, Bhutan, Nepal and even Srilanka. Though over the years, India has uplifted its position in the Human Development Index (HDI) by the better performance of the indicators, it still lies in the medium category of human development. Finally, the paper summarizes and concludes with policy suggestions.

Keywords: Human development, health, education, countries, India

The nature of development has been changing since the early 1990s. Before that, the development was often viewed as a process of economic growth measured by gross domestic product (GDP). Over the years, the focus of the development has changed from growth-oriented to human life enhancement. The United Nations Development Program (UNDP) during 1990 has introduced the concept of Human Development which indicates the enlargement of human choice and capabilities which enabling them to enjoy a higher freedom. United Nations Development Programme Human Development Report (1990). The main argument behind introducing was for viewing development as the process of enhancing people's capabilities for improving the quality of human life. Human development is defined as a process of enlarging people's choices to lead a long and healthy life, to acquire knowledge and be educated, and to have access to resources needed for a decent level of living. United Nations Development Programme Human Development Report (1990). To compare the level of human development across countries and regions, the UNDP constructed the Human Development Index. The Human Development Index (HDI) is a summary measure of three dimensions of human well-being, viz, a long and healthy life, education, and a decent standard of living, United Nations Development Programme Human Development Report (1990). So HDI is usually constructed by combining three indices, which are life expectancy index, education index and the income index. The per capita real income is usually considered a means of good living and a catch-all variable capturing those aspects

of well-being not well represented by life expectancy or literacy (Ghosh, 2006). Although the conventional measure of well-being such as per capita income does not capture the wider aspects of well-being as represented by HDI, it is a predominant means in advancing human development. So there exists a strong link between human development and economic growth, as it considers the development of humans as a whole by means of the three indices. In this backdrop, this paper aims to analyse the progress of India in terms of human development with a comparison to its other neighbour countries. The paper also briefly discusses the performance of human development components in India with available statistics and examines the progress over the years.

Review of Literature

Gerring et al. (2012) examined how the democracy of a country helps to improve the overall human development of a country and they concluded that democracy and human development are time-dependent and historical aspects. Differently, Joshi (2015) commented on the position of India in the Human Development Index and the factors contributing to the scenario. In addition to this, Chawla et al. (2022) investigated the Human Development Index extensively among Indian states and union territories and identified the factors responsible for the condition of well-being of the states. Paul and Mondal (2019) highlighted the basic concepts of HDI and its uses and also analyzed the factors responsible for lagging of India in HDI ranking. Raj et al. (2023) mainly focused on the relationship between growth and development using the data from 1990-2019. The authors observed that the economically weak and low Human Development states can catch the economically strong and high HDI states if there are similar conditions prevail. The report 'Gendering Human Development' (2021) measured the Human Development Index and Gender Development Index for the years 2011-12 and 2017-18 for all the Indian states and union territories and observed that the position of India has increased over the years in terms of performance of both indices. Gerring et al. (2012) examined how the democracy of a country helps to improve the overall human development of a country and they concluded that democracy and human development are time-dependent and historical aspects.

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I have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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Objective of the Study

The basic objective of this paper is to examine the position of India in the human development index and how it has progressed over the years. As India is heading towards the path of development in different respects, so in this regard, this paper examines the status of India in terms of its human development, as it is one of the primary issue for the development of a country. The first part of this paper focuses on the position of India in the Human Development Index with a comparison to its neighbour countries. The second part focuses on the detailed statistical analysis of the components of the human development index in India over different time periods to assess the improvement of India in the human development index through its components.

Method

The study mainly uses the Human Development Index (HDI) data from the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) Human Development Report of different years. Additionally, for the statistical analysis of human development index components for India, the data is mainly taken from Health Dynamics of India 2025, Rural Health Statistics 2007, Economic Survey of India, and Handbook of Statistics on Indian Economy published by Reserve Bank of India.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 represents the year-wise value of the Human Development Index of India with its neighbour countries from the period 1990 to 2023. The analysis reveals that the value of HDI has been increasing gradually through the entire period for India as well as the other considered neighbour countries in this study. China reflects the highest value of HDI among all other considered South East Asian countries during 2023, followed by Sri Lanka. Shi (2024) examined the role of human capital and other institutional, demographic and technological factors that contribute to human development in China. Notably, from the period 1990-2015, the value of HDI in Sri Lanka exceeded the value of China, but after that China was in the leading position in human development index among all other South East Asian countries. The values suggest that India with its other neighbour countries like Bhutan, Nepal, Myanmar, and Bangladesh belongs to the category of medium human development while China and Sri Lanka lie in the category of high human development and Pakistan only belongs to the low human development category. It is observed that China, Sri Lanka and Bhutan were ahead of India in terms of their position in HDI during 2023, while Myanmar and Pakistan were behind India. Surprisingly, during 2023, India and Bangladesh share almost the same value of HDI, though the value of Bangladesh was initially lower than India for the period 1990-2015.

The high value of HDI in Sri Lanka may be due to the free education and health services being provided to all citizens and various social welfare programs to assist the poor, which have been continuing for more than five to six decades (Nanayakkara, 2017). So the better performance of Sri Lanka in HDI was mainly due to the health and education components. The performance of China in the human development index is remarkable, as it is the only country that moved from low human development to high human development since the UNDP's first report on human development. (Liu et al., 2023). The better performance of China in the human development index can be mainly attributed to substantial economic

growth, government investment in education and development of medical technology, which eventually increased the standard of living (Luo et al., 2023; Lu, 2023).

The position of Bhutan in the human development index is also notable due to its high value. The upliftment of Bhutan in human development index was mainly due to its Gross National Happiness (GNH) index, which assess a person's level of sufficiency on 33 happiness conditions (Alkire, 2013). Thus, the Gross National Happiness (GNH) index has an influence to prioritize the citizens' holistic well being and also safeguards the rights of future generations (Brooks, 2013; & Alkire & Zangmo, 2023). In this regard, Vikash (2019) studied the relationship between the Human development index and Gross National Human Development Index and commented that these two indices share almost the same issues, so they are complementary to each other rather than substitutes.

On the other hand, starting with the low value of the human development index, Bangladesh achieved almost the same value as India during 2023. This progress of Bangladesh was due to the improvement in socio-economic indicators such as poverty reduction, educational attainment, increase in life expectancy and decline in maternal and infant mortality rate (Methan et al., 2022). Besides the government, the non-governmental organizations have also played a pivotal role in promoting the socio-economic development of Bangladesh (National Human Development Report Bangladesh, 2021). In case of India, the improvement in HDI was mainly due to the improvement in non-income components such as health and education, rather than income components (Raj et al., 2023). According to the UNDP Human Development Report (2025), India experienced the highest life expectancy since the inception of the index, which suggested a strong recovery from the pandemic.

Myanmar is lagging behind India in terms of its position in the human development index mainly due to the poor performance of human development indicators, which can be attributed to the poor infrastructure and health facilities and overall limited teaching facilities (Pollen, 2024). Pakistan lies in the low human development category and it is examined that health and education have been a low priority for Pakistan's federal and provincial governments, as the budgetary allocation reflects (Mughal & Baig, 2024). According to the Human Development Report (2025) by UNDP, Pakistan's progress slowed to a 35-year low with no clear recovery from the COVID pandemic.

The Value of Human Development Index and its Components in India during 2023

Table 2 represents the country-wise components of HDI during 2023. It is observed that the life expectancy of China and Sri Lanka was roughly same and both of them were leading in this respect among the other considered South East Asian countries followed by Bangladesh and Bhutan. In case of mean years of schooling China was leading, followed by Nepal and Bhutan, whereas in the case of mean years of schooling Sri Lanka was leading followed by China among the other countries considered in this study. GNI per capita was also the highest in China, followed by Bhutan and Sri Lanka during the considered period.

The position of India in the human development index was quite justified by the value of its components as they were mostly lower than the values of China, Sri Lanka and Bhutan and higher than Pakistan and Myanmar. On the other hand, among all the considered

South East Asian countries in this study, Pakistan was the only country that lies in the low human development category and it can

also be justified by the value of its components, which were lowest in all respects.

Table 1

Year-wise Human Development Index of India and its Neighbour Countries

	1990	2000	2010	2015	2020	2021	2022	2023
Countries								
India	0.446	0.501	0.59	0.633	0.652	0.647	0.676	0.685
China	0.491	0.598	0.710	0.750	0.786	0.794	0.796	0.797
Nepal	0.404	0.471	0.551	0.575	0.599	0.596	0.605	0.622
Bhutan	0.427	0.55	0.593	0.637	0.688	0.691	0.695	0.698
Bangladesh	0.397	0.477	0.561	0.621	0.663	0.663	0.680	0.685
Myanmar	0.347	0.415	0.515	0.566	0.609	0.605	0.606	0.609
Sri Lanka	0.638	0.702	0.748	0.769	0.780	0.777	0.777	0.776
Pakistan	0.396	0.436	0.500	0.527	0.536	0.537	0.544	0.544

Note. Source: Human Development Report

Table 2

The Value of Human Development Index and its Components during 2023 for India and its Neighbour Countries

Countries	Human Development Index (HDI)	Life expectancy at birth	Expected years of schooling	Mean years of schooling	Gross national income (GNI) per capita	Rank in HDI
India	0.685	72	13	6.9	9047	133
China	0.797	78	15.5	8	22,029	74
Nepal	0.622	70.4	13.8	4.5	4726	150
Bhutan	0.698	73	13.2	5.8	13,843	126
Bangladesh	0.685	74.7	12.3	6.8	8498	131
Myanmar	0.609	66.9	11.5	6.4	4919	149
Srilanka	0.776	77.5	13.1	10.8	12,616	88
Pakistan	0.544	67.6	7.9	4.3	5501	168

Note. Source: Human Development Report

Gender-wise Value of GDI, HDI and its Components during 2023 for India and its Neighbor Countries

Table 3 computes the human development index and its components separately for male and female workers during 2023 for India and its neighbor countries. It is explored that the value of human development index was lower for female than their male counterparts for all the considered countries during the mentioned period. The difference between the male and female values of HDI

was comparatively higher in China, whereas the difference was smaller in Sri Lanka, Bhutan, and Myanmar.

A detailed analysis of the components reveals that life expectancy was higher for the females than the males for all the considered South East Asian countries and it was highest in China and Sri Lanka, whereas it was lowest in Myanmar and Pakistan during 2023. There was not much difference in the values of mean and expected years of schooling between the male and female workers across the

Table 3

The value of GDI, HDI and its Components for Males and Females during 2023 for India and its Neighbour Countries

Countries	Human Development Index (HDI)		Life expectancy at birth		Expected years of schooling		Mean years of schooling		Gross national income (GNI) per capita		Gender Development Index	
	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Male	Female	Value	Group
India	0.722	0.631	70.5	73.6	13	12.9	5.8	8	13273	4543	0.874	5
China	0.976	0.786	75.2	80.9	15.1	16	8.3	7.8	27,580	16,257	0.976	1
Nepal	0.661	0.567	68.8	71.8	12.4	14	5.8	3.5	6390	3185	0.858	5
Bhutan	0.711	0.681	71.3	75	12.6	13.7	6.3	5.2	16,531	10,750	0.958	2
Bangladesh	0.708	0.658	73	76	11.9	12.4	7.3	6.2	11,820	5,280	0.918	4
Myanmar	0.622	0.589	63.8	70.2	11.1	12	6.7	6.1	6,731	3122	0.947	3
Sri Lanka	0.789	0.750	74.2	80.6	12.6	13.6	10.8	10.7	18,773	6,790	0.951	2
Pakistan	0.579	0.485	65.3	70.2	8.6	7.3	4.6	4	8,724	2,173	0.838	5

Note. Source: Human Development Report

considered countries. In most of the considered countries, the expected years of schooling were higher for the female workers whereas the mean years of schooling were higher for the male workers, irrespective of their position in human development index. Gross national income per capita was mostly higher for males for all the considered countries and the difference was high enough, which indicates the deprived condition of women. Though China was in a leading position in terms of GNI per capita of females followed by Bhutan, the difference was very high to describe the poor condition of females. These low rewards for females were primarily due to the inequality, as females were primarily considered as the caregivers of society, so their participation in economic activities was very much restricted which creates obstacles to their path of development. Further, occupational segregation, violence at the workplace were also some factors that restricted the active participation of females in the labour market. Jayachandran (2014) stated that although actual female labour force participation in rich developed countries was not so systematic but the attitudes of women towards the labour force were more progressive.

Statistical Analysis of Human Development Components of India

Life Expectancy at Birth: This section graphically describes the components of HDI in India to assess the progress of the country over the years through its components. Figure 1 shows the increment of Sub-Center (SC), Primary Health Centre (PHC) and Community Health Centre (CHC) functioning in rural areas between 2005 and 2023, while Figure 2 shows the increase in the number of specialists like General Physician, Gynae and Obstetrics, Pediatrics in Rural areas during the same period. The statistics of rural India have been mainly considered in this study, as it is lagging behind the urban areas in terms of modern and better health facilities. So the first two figures overall suggest an improvement of the rural health facilities over the years, from where the people get benefitted, which has been proved by the fall in the mortality rate (Figure 3) in both rural and urban India during 2006 to 2020. So this evidence is quite enough to state the overall improving health condition of India with the increase in the years of life expectancy.

Figure 1

Number of SC, PHC and CHC Functioning in Rural Area

Note. Source- Health Dynamics of India 2024 Rural Health Statistics 2006

Figure 2

Total Specialists (Surgeon, OB& GY, Physicians, Padiatricians) at CHC in Rural Area

Note. Source- Health Dynamics of India 2024

Figure 3

Fall in the Death Rate between 2005 & 2020

Note. Source- Health Dynamics of India 2024, Rural Health Statistics 20241

Education: Figure 4 shows the overall improvement in the gross enrollment ratio for the periods 2005-06, 2014-15 and 2019-20. Additionally, Figure 5 reflects the gender wise gross enrollment ratio between the periods 2014-15 and 2019-20, which also shows a marginal improvement in the male gross enrollment ratio and a steady increase in the female gross enrollment ratio.

Figure 4

Gross Enrollment Ratio for the Period 2005-06, 2014, & 2019-20

Note. Source: Economic Survey of India

Figure 5

Gross Enrollment Ratio for the Age Group (18-23) for the Males and Females during 2014-15 & 2019-20

Note. Source: Economic Survey of India

GNI Per Capita: Figure 6 shows the increase in GNI per capita over the years. GNI per capita can be obtained by dividing a country's gross national income by its total population. It is observed that per capita GNI has been increasing gradually from 2017-18 to 2020-21 and between 2020-21 to 2021-22, there was a huge increase in GNI per capita and after that it again increased steadily.

Figure 6

Per Capita GNI of 2017-18 2018-19 2019-20 2020-21 2021-22 2022-23 2023-24 (amount in Rs. Crore)

Note. Source: Handbook of Statistics on Indian Economy (Reserve Bank of India)

Summary and Conclusion

This paper examines the position of India in the human development index with respect to its neighboring countries over the period. The performance of different human development indicators has been examined for India as well as for the other neighboring countries in 2023. The study also analyses gender wise human development along with its indicators to examine the level of differences in the development between men and women in India during 2023. The global comparison reveals that India falls into the medium category of human development and it stands behind China, Nepal, Bhutan, and even Sri Lanka in the human development index. Though the analysis reveals that, over the years India has improved in terms of human development with its other neighboring countries but still, India was lagging behind China, Nepal, Bhutan & Sri Lanka, and it almost shares the same value with Bangladesh. In our analysis, only Myanmar and Pakistan were behind India, which was also justified by their value of human development components. The Gender Development Index (GDI) clearly indicates the level of disparity between males and females in terms of different human development components during 2023. India belongs to group 5 in THE Gender Development Index suggesting a wider disparity in enjoying the rights and freedoms between men and women.

The next part of this paper statistically analyses the human development components for India and examines how they have improved over the years. It is observed that all three components have improved over the years resulting a better human development and increased choice of freedom for the people in India. Though the position of India in the human development index has been uplifted in recent years, it is still lagging behind many developing countries

and is placed in the medium human development category.

Several policies can be adopted to uplift India more in a higher position in the human development index, which includes: modernized health facilities in rural areas, subsidized health facilities for common rural people and increasing awareness among the people for contagious diseases. Additionally, to reduce the dropout rate and increase enrollment in the school, different cash transfer schemes have to be provided, especially to the poor families who usually send their son child to the labour market for supportive income and get their daughter child married at an early age. Finally, gross national income per capita can either be increased by increasing the national income as a whole or by adopting different population control measures, which itself enhance the per capita income.

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Received October 10, 2025

Revision received October 27, 2025

Accepted October 30, 2025